

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-142-IBN-5-10% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 142
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	12/7/2022 3:49:46 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 9:02:29 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.574	4601964	49.60	466188
2	8.354	4676288	50.40	408352

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-138-IBN-5-10% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230214
Vial:	55	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 138
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	2/14/2023 10:24:36 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/21/2023 3:33:49 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.389	17851055	97.86	1466093
2	8.170	390989	2.14	28272